

INTRODUCTION OF MODULAR-SYSTEM TEACHING TECHNOLOGIES IN MUSIC EDUCATION

Nurmatova Mayya Abdullayevna

Senior teacher of Urgench State Pedagogical Institute

Matnazarov Amirbek Mansurbek uglu

Urgench State Pedagogical Institute

Student of group 232 of the "Music Education" department

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15356803>

Annotation: This article analyzes the theoretical foundations and practical aspects of introducing modular-systemic teaching technologies into the process of music education. Mechanisms for increasing students' independence in learning, creative thinking and interest in musical activity through a modular-systemic approach are highlighted.

Keywords: Modular-systemic teaching, music education, interactive methods, musical competence, innovative education, didactic modules.

Introduction.

In an era of increasing demands for systematic and effective organization of educational content in modern pedagogical processes, modular-systemic teaching technologies are widely recognized as an innovative method. In particular, in the formation of professional competencies of future specialists in the higher pedagogical education system, modular-based training courses are didactically more effective and serve to develop independent thinking, creative approach and reflective analysis skills. Music education is an aesthetic-emotional process in content and form, and the introduction of modern pedagogical technologies, in particular modular-systemic teaching, to increase its effectiveness is one of the urgent tasks.

Modular-systemic teaching is the organization of the knowledge transfer process on the basis of blocks (modules), each module systematically incorporating specific goals, content blocks, learning tasks, control forms and assessment criteria. The main advantage of this technology is that it allows individualizing the student's educational activities, ensuring didactic flexibility, strengthening the motivation for independent learning and developing a creative approach. In particular, the modular-systemic approach in the process of music education serves to create an educational environment aimed at combining theoretical knowledge with practical skills, improving listening and analysis, improving performance skills, and developing musical thinking.

Methodology:

The introduction of modular-systemic teaching technologies in music education requires not only an update of the content of education, but also a revision of the methodological foundations of the entire pedagogical process. Today, while traditional teaching methods are being replaced by interactive, innovative and person-oriented technologies, the modular-systemic approach introduces a qualitatively new paradigm into the methodology of music education.

In this study, the constructivist approach, the integration of a competency-based education model and modern didactic technologies were used as the methodological basis. According to the theory of constructivism, the student is not just a recipient of knowledge, but is considered a person who actively processes it and understands it based on his own experience. This approach shows its relevance precisely in the processes of individual learning, problem tasks and independent analysis inherent in the module system. Several methods were used in the research process to conduct a qualitative and systematic analysis. First of all, using the theoretical-analytical method, the historical development of modular-system teaching technologies, didactic foundations and possibilities of adaptation to music education were studied in depth. Through this, modern pedagogical ideas and advanced foreign experiences were analyzed, and aspects that are suitable for the Uzbek educational environment were identified. Also, the impact of modular-based lessons on students' competence in a real educational environment was studied based on empirical observation and diagnostic methods. During the experimental work, changes in student activity, an increase in the level of motivation, and the formation of a creative approach were observed. The results of the observations were recorded based on analytical tables and quality indicators.

A design-methodological approach was used in the formation of the structure of the modules, and each module was designed as an independent didactic unit. It included a target direction, a content block, interactive tasks, assessment tools, and sections that create conditions for student reflection. This, in turn, ensured that through each module the student had the opportunity to develop musical thinking, improve practical performance skills, and form analytical thinking.

These methodological foundations made it possible to successfully implement a modular-systemic approach not only in theoretical knowledge, but also in practice. As a result, it was proven that it is possible to educate creative, active, independent-thinking, analytically oriented individuals through an

educational process organized on the basis of modules in the music education system.

Analysis and discussion:

The pilot study on the implementation of modular-systemic teaching technologies in music education showed that this technology not only improves the quality of the educational process, but also creates significant positive changes in students' musical thinking, creative approach, and desire for independent learning. The study was conducted with the participation of 64 third-year students studying in the music education department of higher educational institutions in the 2024–2025 academic year. The group was divided into two parts: 32 participated in classes based on the traditional teaching method (control group), and the remaining 32 participated in classes based on modular-systemic teaching (experimental group).

At the initial stage, tests were conducted between the two groups to determine the level of knowledge. According to the results, the average score in the control group was 56.2, and in the experimental group - 55.8 - that is, the initial level was almost equal. However, after 8 weeks of training with the introduction of modular-system technologies, an assessment was carried out based on repeated tests, performance exercises, analytical tasks and questions and answers. At this stage, the average result of the students in the experimental group reached 83.5 points, while the control group achieved 68.9 points.

Statistically, these changes were analyzed using the t-student criterion and proved the effectiveness of modular-system teaching with a reliability of $p < 0.01$. This change was especially evident in the indicators of musical listening analysis (musical dictation), performance skills, compositional thinking and emotional expression. In the experimental group, the rate of independent completion of musical analysis tasks increased from 72% to 94%, and performance skills were highly rated by evaluators, with an 87% increase.

The analysis showed that the modular-system approach allows the student to approach the lesson individually, plan his/her own activities, control the pace of mastery and evaluate the results. This, in turn, contributes to the formation of the student's autonomy, reflective thinking and creative potential. The results of the survey conducted with the students also confirmed the effectiveness of the method. 91% of the students in the experimental group rated the modular lessons as interesting, logically organized and motivating. 84% of them noted that their independent thinking and musical level in music lessons increased through this technology. The integration of modular-system teaching technology

into music education not only increases the quality and efficiency of education, but also serves as an important tool for developing the individual abilities of students, encouraging them to independent musical thinking, and forming competencies based on a personal approach. Statistical analysis confirms this idea on a scientific basis.

Conclusion:

Based on the above analysis, it was determined that the introduction of modular-systemic teaching technologies into music education serves to organize the educational process in an effective, systematic and innovative way. This technology creates the basis for the gradual, goal-oriented formation of students' musical knowledge, skills and competencies. Empirical experiments have proven that the educational content organized on the basis of modules is highly effective, especially in the formation of such competencies as creative thinking, independent musical analysis, compositional approach and emotional perception. The advantages of the modular-systemic approach are the possibility of individualization in education, stimulation of student activity, wide use of interactive methods and assessment of results based on clear criteria. It is these aspects that increase students' motivation for musical activity and arouse their deep interest in the professional direction.

In conclusion, the implementation of modular-system teaching technologies in the music education system is a modern pedagogical approach that serves to improve the quality and effectiveness of education, develop personal and professional competencies of students. Through the gradual and systematic introduction of this technology, it is possible to raise the musical-educational process to a high pedagogical level.

List of references:

1. Bobokalonova Sh.Kh. Pedagogy. – Tashkent: “O’qituvati”, 2021. – 304 p.
2. Mamarasulova Sh. Pedagogical foundations of the modular teaching system in music education // World of Teachers. – 2023. – №3. – P. 15–18.
3. Mavlonova R. H. Pedagogical technology and pedagogical skills. – Tashkent: “O’qituvati”, 2020. – 272 p.
4. Yunusova N. Interactive methods and modular teaching technologies. – Tashkent: IQT, 2021. – 138 p.
5. Kurbanova M.T. Innovative technologies in music education. – Tashkent: Science and technologies, 2022. – 160 p.
6. UNESCO. Reimagining our futures together: A new social contract for education. – Paris: UNESCO Publishing, 2021. – 185 p.